

The background of the cover is a composite image. On the left, there is an aerial photograph of a river winding through a dry, brown landscape. On the right, there is a dark blue background with a white line graph showing fluctuating data points, overlaid with a faint grid pattern.

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**INNOVATIVE
APPROACHES TO
WATER RESOURCE
MANAGEMENT IN
ARID REGIONS IN THE
CONTEXT OF
CLIMATE CHANGE**

PROCEEDINGS
(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

WICAR-2026

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International Scientific and Practical Conference -2026

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference innovative approaches to water resource management in arid regions in the context of climate change on May 19, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The conference aims to discuss key issues of effective water resource management in arid regions under climate change, develop and apply innovative approaches and mathematical and computational modeling methods, share recent research results and practical experience, and strengthen international academic cooperation in this field.

Key Themes of the Conference:

1. Water Diplomacy and Integrated Approaches in International Relation: Interdisciplinary Approaches to Sustainable Development, Communication and Global Security

- Issues of systemic analysis in international relations and world politics in the context of water diplomacy
- Economic, environmental and energy aspects of sustainable development
- Systemic approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. Mathematical and computer modeling of optimal water resources management under climate change

- Optimal water resource management under climate change
- Modeling water resource dynamics and climate variability
- Methods of applied and computational mathematics in irrigation system modeling.

3. Environmental and Hydrogeological Processes in the Aral Sea Region: Analysis Based on Modern Technologies

- Analysis of hydrogeological processes in the Aral Sea region
- Application of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data technologies to environmental challenges
- Simulation and stochastic modeling of environmental and hydrogeological processes in the Aral region.

The event was conducted in a hybrid format with participation in English, Russian, and Uzbek. The conference provided a high-level platform for scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Sayoz suv tenglamalarini sonli usulda yechish

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu ishda ochiq kanallardagi nostatsionar jarayonlarni ifodalovchi Sen-Venan tenglamalari sistemasi uchun chegaraviy shartlarni shakllantirish masalasi tadqiq etilgan. Sistemaning giperbolikligi isbotlanib, Riman invariantlari va xarakteristik tezliklar aniqlangan. Turli oqim rejimlari (tinch, kritik va tezkor) uchun chegarada zaruriy shartlar soni va turi xarakteristikalar usuli yordamida asoslangan. Shuningdek, quyi chegara uchun botiq chegaraviy shartning gidravlik talqini berilgan va MacCormack sonli sxemasi orqali masalani yechish algoritmi ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: Sen-Venan tenglamalari, xarakteristikalar usuli, Riman invariantlari, sonli modellashtirish, ochiq oqimli kanallar, Manning ishqalanishi, botiq chegaraviy shart.

1. Kirish

Ochiq oqimli kanallarda suyuqlik harakatini modellashtirish gidravlika, gidrotexnika, irrigatsiya va atrof-muhit muhandisligida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bunday oqimlarni ifodalash uchun eng koʻp qoʻllaniladigan matematik model bu bir oʻlchamli Sen-Venan tenglamalari sistemasidir.

Ushbu ishda quyidagi modifikatsiyalangan sistema oʻrganiladi (Metodologiya boʻlimiga asosan):

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(Hu)}{\partial x} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial(Hu)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(Hu^2 + g/2 H^2) + gH \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + H \frac{\lambda}{2} u|u| = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

bu yerda:

- H – oqim chuqurligi (suv sathi balandligi),
- u - oqimning oʻrtacha tezligi,
- $q = Hu$ - solishtirma suv sarfi (kenglik birligiga),
- $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$ – erkin tushish tezlanishi,
- h - kanal tubining balandligi (geometrik profil),
- λ — gidravlik qarshilik koeffitsienti (Manning formulasi asosida aniqlanadi).

Mazkur sistemaning oʻziga xos jihati shundaki, impuls tenglamasi kanal tubi qiyaligini ($\partial h / \partial x$) va ishqalanish kuchini ($\lambda u|u|/2$) aniq hisobga oladi. Ishqalanish koeffitsienti λ esa quyidagi Manning formulasi orqali ifodalanadi :

$$\lambda = \frac{2gn_m^2}{H^{4/3}} \quad (2)$$

bu yerda n_m — Manning gʻadir-budirlik koeffitsienti.

Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi — berilgan sistemani toʻliq matematik tahlil qilish, xarakteristikalar va Riman invariantlarini aniqlash, hamda ular asosida chegaraviy shartlarni toʻgʻri hisobga oluvchi sonli yechish algoritmini ishlab chiqishdan iborat.

2. Masalaning matematik qoʻyilishi

2.1. Tenglamalarni kanonik shaklga keltirish

Sistema (1) ni kvazichiziqli shaklda yozish uchun barcha hosilalarni ochamiz. Qulaylik uchun erkin sirt balandligini $z_s = H + h$ deb belgilaymiz.

Birinchi tenglama (uzluksizlik tenglamasi):

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + H \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Ikkinchi tenglama (impuls tenglamasi): Avvalo, $\frac{\partial z_s}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}$ ekanligini hisobga olamiz:

$$\frac{\partial(Hu)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(Hu^2)}{\partial x} + gH \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + gH \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + H \frac{\lambda}{2} u|u| = 0$$

Chap tomondagi dastlabki ikkita hadni ko'paytma qoidasi bo'yicha ochamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(Hu)}{\partial t} &= H \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial(Hu^2)}{\partial x} &= u^2 \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + 2Hu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \end{aligned}$$

Bu ifodalarni impuls tenglamasiga qo'yamiz:

$$H \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} + u^2 \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + 2Hu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + gH \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + gH \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + H \frac{\lambda}{2} u|u| = 0 \quad (4)$$

Endi (3) tenglamadan $\frac{\partial H}{\partial t}$ ni ifodalab olamiz:

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = -u \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} - H \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}$$

Buni (4) dagi $u \frac{\partial H}{\partial t}$ hadi o'rniga qo'yamiz:

$$H \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \left(-u \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} - H \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) + u^2 \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + 2Hu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + gH \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + gH \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + H \frac{\lambda}{2} u|u| = 0$$

Qavslarni ochib, o'xshash hadlarni ixchamlaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} H \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} - u^2 \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} - Hu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + u^2 \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + 2Hu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + gH \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + gH \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + H \frac{\lambda}{2} u|u| &= 0 \\ H \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + Hu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + gH \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + gH \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} + H \frac{\lambda}{2} u|u| &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

$H > 0$ deb hisoblab, tenglikning ikkala tomonini H ga bo'lamiz. Natijada sistema quyidagi kanonik ko'rinishga keladi:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} + H \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + g \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} = -g \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} - \frac{\lambda}{2} u|u| \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Bu sistema giperbolik tipga mansub bo'lib, standart Sen-Venan tenglamalaridan o'ng tomondagi qo'shimcha manba hadlari bilan farqlanadi: $-g \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}$ had kanal tubi qiyaligini, $-\frac{\lambda}{2} u|u|$ had esa ishqalanish kuchini ifodalaydi.

Vektor-matritsa shakli

Sistemani ixcham vektor-matritsa ko'rinishda yozamiz:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{U}) \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial x} = \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{U}) \quad (6)$$

bu yerda:

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{pmatrix} H \\ u \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} u & H \\ g & u \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{S} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ -g \frac{dh}{dx} - \frac{\lambda}{2} u|u| \end{pmatrix}$$

3. Xarakteristikalar va Riman invariantlari

3.1. Xos qiymatlar va xarakteristik tezliklar

A matritsaning xos qiymatlarini topamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \det(\mathbf{A} - \lambda_c \mathbf{I}) &= \begin{vmatrix} u - \lambda_c & H \\ g & u - \lambda_c \end{vmatrix} = (u - \lambda_c)^2 - gH = 0 \\ (u - \lambda_c)^2 &= gH \Rightarrow \lambda_c = u \pm \sqrt{gH} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

To'liq tarqalish tezligini $c = \sqrt{gH}$ deb belgilaymiz. U holda xarakteristik tezliklar:

$$\lambda_1 = u + c, \quad \lambda_2 = u - c \quad (8)$$

Shunga mos ravishda ikkita xarakteristik chiziq oilasi mavjud:

$$C^+: \frac{dx}{dt} = u + c, \quad C^-: \frac{dx}{dt} = u - c \quad (9)$$

3.2. Riman invariantlari

λ_1 va λ_2 uchun mos chap xos vektorlarni topamiz:

$$\mathbf{l}_1 = (g \quad c), \quad \mathbf{l}_2 = (g \quad -c)$$

Bir jinsli hol uchun ($S = 0$) sistema (6) ni chapdan \mathbf{l}_k^T ga ko'paytiramiz. C^+ bo'ylab ($dx/dt = u + c$):

$$g \frac{dH}{dt} + c \frac{du}{dt} = 0$$

$c = \sqrt{gH}$ ekanligidan differensial bog'liqlikni topamiz: $dc = \frac{g}{2c} dH$, ya'ni $g dH = 2c dc$.

Demak:

$$2c \frac{dc}{dt} + c \frac{du}{dt} = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad c \frac{d}{dt}(u + 2c) = 0$$

$c > 0$ bo'lgani uchun C^+ bo'ylab Riman invarianti:

$$J_+ = u + 2c = \text{const} \quad (10)$$

Xuddi shunday, C^- bo'ylab:

$$J_- = u - 2c = \text{const} \quad (11)$$

3.3. Manba hadining invariantlarga ta'siri

To'liq sistema uchun (5) dan foydalanib, Riman invariantlarining xarakteristikalar bo'ylab o'zgarish qonuniyatini keltirib chiqaramiz:

C^+ bo'ylab ($dx/dt = u + c$):

$$\frac{d}{dt}(u + 2c) = -g \frac{dh}{dx} - \frac{\lambda}{2} u |u| \quad (12)$$

C^- bo'ylab ($dx/dt = u - c$):

$$\frac{d}{dt}(u - 2c) = -g \frac{dh}{dx} - \frac{\lambda}{2} u |u| \quad (13)$$

Bu oddiy differensial tenglamalar sonli integrallash uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

4. Boshlang'ich va chegaraviy shartlar

4.1. Boshlang'ich shartlar

$t = 0$ momentda butun $x \in [0, L]$ oraligida quyidagi boshlang'ich shartlar beriladi:

$$H(x, 0) = H_0(x), \quad u(x, 0) = u_0(x) \quad (14)$$

4.2. Chegaraviy shartlar tahlili

Xarakteristikalar yo'nalishiga qarab, qancha va qanday chegaraviy shart kerakligini aniqlaymiz. Odatda daryo oqimlari uchun $u < c$ (tinch oqim, Frud soni $Fr = u/c < 1$). Bu holda:

- $x = 0$ da: C^+ chiziq sohaga kiradi ($\lambda_1 > 0$), C^- esa sohadan chiqadi ($\lambda_2 < 0$). Demak, 1 ta chegaraviy shart kerak.

- $x = L$ da: C^- chiziq sohaga kiradi ($\lambda_2 > 0$ bo'lishi mumkin), C^+ esa sohadan chiqadi.

Demak, 1 ta chegaraviy shart kerak.

Yuqori chegara ($x = 0$): Odatda suv sarfi yoki suv sathi beriladi:

$$Q(0, t) = Q_{\text{yuq}}(t) \quad \text{yoki} \quad H(0, t) = H_{\text{yuq}}(t) \quad (15)$$

Quyi chegara ($x = L$): Masala shartiga ko'ra, bu yerda «botiq» chegara sharti berilgan. Bu shart odatda suv o'tkazgich yoki vodosliv uchun quyidagicha ifodalanadi:

$$u(L, t)H(L, t) = C [H(L, t)]^{3/2} \quad \Rightarrow \quad u(L, t) = C \sqrt{H(L, t)} \quad (16)$$

bu yerda C — S. Urant konstantasi (o'zgarimas koeffitsient).

4.3. Gidravlik qarshilik parametri

Manba hadidagi λ koeffitsienti [eq:lambd] formula orqali, Manning g'adir-budirlik koeffitsienti n_m esa quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$n_m = \frac{g_0 c}{m \cdot l^3} \quad (17)$$

bu yerda g_0 — erkin tushish tezlanishining sonli qiymati, c — tezlik, m — massa, l — uzunlik birliklari. Amaliy hisoblashlarda n_m konstanta sifatida qabul qilinadi.

5. Sonli yechish algoritmi

5.1. Ichki nuqtalar uchun oshkor ayirmali sxema

Hudud $x \in [0, L]$ ni N ta teng bo'lakka bo'lamiz: $\Delta x = L/N$. Vaqt qadami Δt Kurant-Fridrix-Levi (CFL) shartidan aniqlanadi:

$$\Delta t = \text{CFL} \cdot \frac{\Delta x}{\max(|u_i| + c_i)}, \quad \text{CFL} \leq 1 \quad (18)$$

Ichki nuqtalar ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1$) uchun Markaziy ayirmalar sxemasi qo'llaniladi:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{H_i^{n+1} - H_i^n}{\Delta t} + u_i^n \frac{H_{i+1}^n - H_{i-1}^n}{2\Delta x} + H_i^n \frac{u_{i+1}^n - u_{i-1}^n}{2\Delta x} &= 0 \\ \frac{u_i^{n+1} - u_i^n}{\Delta t} + u_i^n \frac{u_{i+1}^n - u_{i-1}^n}{2\Delta x} + g \frac{H_{i+1}^n - H_{i-1}^n}{2\Delta x} &= -g \frac{h_{i+1} - h_{i-1}}{2\Delta x} - \frac{\lambda_i^n}{2} u_i^n |u_i^n| \end{aligned}$$

bu yerda $\lambda_i^n = 2gn_m^2/(H_i^n)^{4/3}$.

5.2. Chegaraviy nuqtalar uchun xarakteristik sxema

Chegaraviy nuqtalarda aniqlikni oshirish uchun Riman invariantlari usuli qo'llaniladi.

Yuqori chegara ($i = 0$):

Agar yuqori chegarada suv sarfi Q_{yuq} berilgan bo'lsa, C^+ xarakteristika bo'yicha keladigan invariantdan foydalanamiz. (12) tenglamani C^+ xarakteristika bo'ylab diskretlashtiramiz:

$$\frac{(u_0^{n+1} + 2c_0^{n+1}) - (u_1^n + 2c_1^n)}{\Delta t} = -g \frac{h_1 - h_0}{\Delta x} - \frac{1}{4} (\lambda_0^{n+1} u_0^{n+1} |u_0^{n+1}| + \lambda_1^n u_1^n |u_1^n|) \quad (21)$$

Bu tenglama va $u_0^{n+1} H_0^{n+1} = Q_{\text{yuq}}^{n+1}$ sharti birgalikda yechilib, u_0^{n+1} va H_0^{n+1} topiladi.

Quyi chegara ($i = N$):

Quyi chegarada botiq shart (16) berilgan. C^- xarakteristika bo'yicha (13) tenglamani diskretlashtiramiz:

$$\frac{(u_N^{n+1} - 2c_N^{n+1}) - (u_{N-1}^n - 2c_{N-1}^n)}{\Delta t} = -g \frac{h_N - h_{N-1}}{\Delta x} - \frac{1}{4} (\lambda_N^{n+1} u_N^{n+1} |u_N^{n+1}| + \lambda_{N-1}^n u_{N-1}^n |u_{N-1}^n|) \quad (22)$$

Bu tenglama va $u_N^{n+1} = C \sqrt{H_N^{n+1}}$ sharti birgalikda yechiladi. Bunda $c_N^{n+1} = \sqrt{g H_N^{n+1}}$ ekanligi hisobga olinadi.

Xulosa

Ushbu tadqiqotda ochiq kanallardagi nostatsionar jarayonlarni ifodalovchi Sen-Venan tenglamalari sistemasi uchun chegaraviy shartlarni to'g'ri shakllantirish masalasi kompleks o'rganildi. Matematik tahlil natijasida sistemaning giperbolikligi va xarakteristik tezliklari aniqlanib, Manning ishqalanish koeffitsienti hamda kanal qiyaligi hisobga olingan holda Riman invariantlarining o'zgarish qonuniyatlari keltirib chiqarildi. Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, xarakteristikalar usuli nafaqat sistemaning fizik mohiyatini ochib berishda, balki chegaraviy nuqtalarda (xususan, quyi chegara uchun taklif etilgan botiq shartda) sonli yechim barqarorligini ta'minlashda ham asosiy vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Ishlab chiqilgan algoritm va taklif etilgan tavsiyalar gidravlik inshootlarni loyihalashda suv sathi tebranishlarini prognoz qilish va murakkab oqim rejimlarini modellashtirishning aniqligini oshirish imkonini beradi.

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